

Dehydrobromination and debromination of 2,2,7 α -tribromocholest-4-en-3,6-dione

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Abstract : The reaction of 2,2,7 α -tribromocholest-4-en-3,6-dione (1) with lithium bromide in *N,N*-dimethyl formamide furnished a single compound identified as 2-bromocholest-1,4-dien-3,6-dione (2) by spectroscopic methods (UV, FT-IR, NMR and Mass).

Keywords : Bromo derivatives, lithium bromide, *N,N*-dimethyl formamide, debromination.

Introduction

Dehydrobromination of triterpenoids of lupane and friedelin skeleton has already been reported from our laboratory¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our studies on the transformative reactions of steroids and triterpenoids⁵⁻⁷ and in order to see the effect of LiBr-DMF on a steroidal skeleton having bromines in different chemical/stereochemical environment, presently we have studied the dehydrobromination of a steroidal skeleton, 2,2,7 α -tribromocholest-4-en-3,6-dione (1), using the same reagent. The isolation and characterization of the product comprises the subject matter of this paper.

Results and discussion

The single compound obtained after refluxing a solution of 2,2,7 α -tribromocholest-4-en-3,6-dione (1) in DMF with LiBr for 6 h was purified by column chromatography. Crystallization of the compound from CHCl₃-MeOH mixture furnished white crystals (2). It is analyzed for C₂₇H₃₉BrO₂, m.p. 182–184 °C, showed positive test for halogen, UV : 259 nm, IR : 1711 cm⁻¹ (α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compound). Mass spectral analysis of the compound 2 showed molecular ions at *m/z* 476, 474 (M⁺) (1 : 1) indicating the presence of one bromine atom in the compound, the other fragments appeared at *m/z* 435, 394, 387, 357, 347, 331, 303, 288, 257, 247, 214, 174. In its ¹H NMR spectrum, compound 2 showed singlet at δ 6.442 ppm integrating for one proton due to C-4 hydrogen and the downfield singlet at 7.275 ppm integrated for one proton is definitely due to the vinyl proton at C-1 position. The double doublet centered at δ 2.699 with *J* 3.3

and 14.7 Hz, is due to the interaction between axial-axial proton of C-7H and C-8H and the other signal appeared as a doublet of a doublet centered at δ 2.133 ppm with *J* 3.3 and 14.7 Hz, indicated that the methylene protons at C-7 coupled with axial proton at C-8. The presence of five methyl groups, three of which appeared as doublets at δ 0.85, 0.88, 0.94 (*J* 0.9, 0.9 and 6.6 Hz respectively) due to the secondary methyls, and two as singlets at δ 0.75 and 1.24 ppm. ¹³C NMR accounted for all 27 carbons in which five are quartets, eight triplets, eight doublets and six singlets; the doublets at δ 153.7 ppm and singlets at 124.3 ppm were due to C-1 and C-2 olefinic carbons, C-3 and C-6 carbonyl carbons appeared as singlets at δ 178.4 ppm and 201.0 ppm [about 5.4 and 7.0 ppm upfield respectively in comparison to that of the parent compound 1]. C-4 and C-5 carbons appeared at δ 123.2 ppm and 161.5 ppm as doublet and singlet respectively. The newly developed C-7 methylene carbon appeared at 46.9 ppm as a triplet. Finally, the structure of compound 2 has been confirmed by the comparison of its ¹³C NMR data with those of cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (A), androst-1,4-diene-3,17-one (B) and compound 1 which is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of carbon-13 chemical shifts (ppm) of compound 2 with those of cholest-4-en-3,6-dione (A), androst-1,4-diene-3,17-one (B) and the starting compound 1

Carbon No.	A	B	1	2
1	35.5	155.2	59.9(t)	153.7(d)
2	33.9	127.6	57.0(s)	124.3(s)
3	199.4	186.0	184.0(s)	178.4(s)
4	125.4	124.0	122.9(d)	123.2(d)

Table-1 (contd.)

5	161.1	168.2	159.0(s)	161.5(s)
6	202.3	32.3	194.0(s)	201.0(s)
7	46.8	31.2	42.4(d)	46.9(t)
8	34.2	35.0	37.4(d)	34.3(d)
9	50.1	52.3	51.9(d)	49.1(d)
10	39.1	43.4	45.7(s)	48.4(s)
11	20.9	22.0	20.5(t)	22.9(t)
12	39.8	32.5	38.4(t)	39.0(t)
13	42.5	47.6	43.4(s)	42.7(s)
14	55.9	50.4	55.6(d)	55.9(d)
15	24.0	21.8	23.7(t)	24.0(t)
16	28.0	35.5	28.0(t)	27.9(t)
17	56.5	219.6	57.6(d)	56.1(d)
18	11.9	13.8	12.4(q)	11.9(q)
19	17.5	18.7	18.6(q)	18.8(q)
20	35.7	-	35.6(d)	35.6(d)
21	18.6	-	18.6(q)	18.6(q)
22	36.1	-	36.0(t)	36.0(t)
23	23.8	-	22.8(t)	23.8(t)
24	39.5	-	39.5(t)	39.4(t)
25	28.0	-	27.7(d)	28.0(d)
26	22.5	-	22.5(q)	22.5(q)
27	22.8	-	22.8(q)	22.8(q)

Discussion of reaction mechanism :

From the above spectral analysis it is evident that dehydrobromination has occurred only in ring (A) leading to the introduction of a C1-C2 double bond. It is also clear from the spectral analysis that a new CH₂ group has developed at C7 of ring (B) during debromination on it. This is interesting since we could observe debromination along with dehydrobromination from α -bromoketone by the use of LiBr-*N,N*-DMA, out of this study. This may be explained by considering the more accessibility of the C1-H for dehydrobromination in comparison to C8-H (situated on a ring juncture carbon) (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Petroleum ether had b.p 60–80 °C. PMR, ¹³C NMR and DEPT spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ Bruker Avance 300 MHz FT NMR spectrometer (chemical shift in δ ppm) using TMS as the internal standard (having suitable deuterated solvent). Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL-AccuTOF JMS-T100LC Mass spectrometer. IR spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrophotometer using KBr discs. UV spectra were taken in a Shimadzu UV-240 spectropho-

tometer in methanol solution. Column chromatography was performed over silica gel (60–120 mesh). TLC was performed over silica gel and developed in an iodine chamber.

Treatment of 2,2,7 α -tribromocholest-4-en-3,6-dione (1) with LiBr-DMF :

2,2,7 α -Tribromocholest-4-en-3,6-dione (1) (0.5 g) was refluxed with LiBr (0.5 g) in DMF (50 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with water, extracted with ether and the residue (0.4 g) from the ether layer was chromatographed over silica gel (18 g). The compound was eluted with petroleum ether (PE)-ethyl acetate (EA) (95 : 5) to furnish compound 2 (0.38 g).

2-Bromocholest-1,4-dien-3,6-dione : It is crystallized from CHCl₃-MeOH, m.p. 182–184 °C; Beilstein test : green flame; IR (KBr) : 1711 cm⁻¹; UV (MeOH) : 259 nm; ¹H NMR : δ 0.75(s), 1.24(s) (2 \times *tert*-Me), 0.85 (d, *J* 0.9 Hz), 0.88 (d, *J* 0.9 Hz), 0.94 (d, *J* 6.6 Hz) (3 \times *sec*-Me), 6.442 (1H, s, H-C-4=C), 7.523 (1H, s, H-C-1=CH), 2.699 (1H, dd, *J* 3.3 and 14.7 Hz), 2.133 (1H, dd, *J* 3.3 and 14.7 Hz); ¹³C NMR : 153.7(C1), 124.3(C2), 178.4(C3), 123.2(C4), 161.5(C5), 201.0(C6) and newly introduced C7 at 46.9 as CH₂. MS : *m/z* 476, 474 (1 : 1) (M⁺), 435, 394, 387, 357, 347, 331, 303, 288, 257, 247, 214, 174.

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